

GLOBALIZATION, ICT AND EDUCATION

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Abstract

Development and innovation of computer technologies have transformed the way education is structured, organized and delivered. Information and Communication technology has advanced in ways which could not be imagined even a decade back. Changes in technology have facilitated dramatic shifts in communication making it easier to connect people in unprecedented ways and require that today's students have the knowledge, skills and dispositions to engage responsibly and effectively in the increasingly globalized context. The education system is now witnessing a paradigm shift from the traditional chalk and talk teaching methodology to digitizing the pedagogical approach through technical devices. Adopting and adapting educational technologies associated with computers and the internet for use with instruction is often transforming not only how we teach, affording new ways to address old problems but also turning attention to some of the basic issues in teaching focusing the educators on the pedagogy itself, its design and its efficacy.

Education Technology provides such teaching learning situations, which brings the best practices or means of instructions which effect on learning positively. There domains of knowledge cover three main areas with respect to techno-pedagogy, which are content, pedagogy, and technology respectively. The subject matter to be taught is referred to as content. Technology includes both modern and everyday technologies such as computers, the internet, and digital video, as well as overhead projectors, blackboards, and books.

Key Words: Globalization, ICT and Education

Introduction

Techno pedagogy skills are related to hybrid teaching style in which ICT is used to teach and learn in a classroom setting. Pedagogy literally translates to “teaching science and art”. The term “techno” is derived from the Latin word “texere” which means “to weave or to create”. Techno is a qualification that intersects or crosses pedagogy's meaning with its own. Thus, Techno-Pedagogy is an art of teaching with the addition of technology to improve academic achievement and also helps in remote learning. Education Technology provides such teaching learning situations, which brings the best practices or means of instructions

which effect on learning positively. There domains of knowledge cover three main areas with respect to techno-pedagogy, which are content, pedagogy, and technology respectively. The subject matter to be taught is referred to as content. Technology includes both modern and everyday technologies such as computers, the internet, and digital video, as well as overhead projectors, blackboards, and books. Pedagogy is the study of teaching and learning techniques, processes, tactics, procedures, and approaches. As a result, Techno-pedagogical abilities refer to a teacher's ability to integrate these main areas of knowledge domain and apply them in a teaching-learning environment. Teachers use ICT facilities to acquire information, generate solutions, analyse, and apply knowledge in teaching learning process by means of their ability or potentiality.

Pedagogies

Some of the important pedagogies and technologies are as follows: -

Cooperative Learning: Is the process of where teacher educators divide a class of students into small groups so that they can work together to learn a new idea. Cooperative learning has been around for a long time, but it has never achieved the same level of popularity as blended learning or differentiated instruction.

Concept Mapping: Can help the teacher educators to visualize relationships between various concepts and test their understanding of complex subjects. Thinking and visually representing relationships between ideas forms mental connections that allow for better retention of knowledge. This is a popular way to capture understanding of a topic for work, school, or personal study. It's used most frequently in academia, but the process can be easily applied to other fields

Blended Learning: Is an approach to learning that combines face-to-face and online learning experiences. Ideally, each (both online and off) will complement the other by using its particular strength.

Flipped Learning: Is that pedagogical technique through which direct instruction transfers from the group learning space to the individual learning space, transforming the group area into a dynamic, interactive learning environment in which the educator supports students as they apply concepts and participate creatively in the subject matter.

Technology

Audio-Visual Technology: The value of audio-visual (AV) technology in teaching cannot be overstated. There are two reasons for this: first, studying through AV offers a vibrant and

interactive environment that is more favourable to learning; and second, we live in an audio-visual age, which means that knowing how to utilise AV equipment is essential for future employment opportunities. As a result, it is critical that students have access to AV technology at school.

Animation: Online learning modules help students learn and retain information more effectively by combining a variety of quirky and fascinating animation technologies. The human brain has also been shown to process and remember information acquired in the audio-visual realm more successfully. As a result, online education channels have grown in tandem with advances in innovation and technology, utilising immersive animation and digital multimedia capabilities to create fascinating real-time educational content that better captures students' attention.

Discussion Forums: Are probably the earliest form of social media platform. Early adopters of Internet technology may recall newsgroups and subcommittees (SIGs) hosted on early Internet-connected websites and systems. These communities were rooted in technical topics, but eventually expanded to cover almost any category that could attract viewers. These platforms have matured and are now hosted on consumer social networking sites.

Assessment and Evaluation: It is an important process through which we can get proper feedback in educational process. By means of MOODLES and with the help of several online apps we can assess the progress of students.

Techno-Pedagogic Skills Includes

Ability to evaluate the benefits and drawbacks of various learning systems.

Ability to do needs assessment in order to introduce technology in a pedagogical order.

Ability to use and troubleshoot basic tools and software, as well as address small technical issues.

Appropriate work plan and design ability.

The ability to plan for crossroads both inside and outside the classroom.

The ability to invest in new and interactive technologies that are compatible with the subject's nature.

The ability to manage time and integrate technologies in the most efficient way possible.

Techno-Pedagogical Skills is basis of effective teaching which refers to electronically mediated skills that integrate pedagogical principles with the use of technology. Techno-

Pedagogy does not mean only use of internet and digital devices/applications but to use technology as means of achieving learning objectives related to content.

Conclusion: We know that techno pedagogical skills are very important for effective output along with sound content knowledge in relation to E- Learning. However, there are various challenges are there for teacher educators regarding this but with the help of proper techno pedagogical skills they can minimize these which further leads to quality education.

Reference

- Parkash, Jai and Hooda, Sushila Rani (2017), "A Study of Techno-Pedagogical Competency Among Teachers of Government & Private Schools of Haryana State", *International Journal of Current Advance Research*, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24327/ijcar.2018.9306.1532>
- Sathiyaraj, K., & Rajasekar, S. (2013), *The Relationship between the Techno-Pedagogical Competency of Higher secondary School Teachers and their Anxiety towards the Use of Instructional Aids in Teaching*. *International Journal of Teacher Educational Research*, 2(12), 7-14.
- Thakur, N. (2015). *A Study on Implementation of Techno-pedagogy Skills, Its Challenges and Role to Release at Higher Level of Education*. *American International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 182-186.
- K. K. Sibichen (2018). *Techno-Pedagogical Skills of Secondary Teacher Education Students*. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 7(12), 887-890. 10.21275/ART20193724
- Ali, M. (2018). *Techno- Pedagogical Competency of Teachers: An Area of Concern in the 21st Century Higher Education*. *Review Of Research*, 7(11), 1-5.